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Charged Lepton Flavour Violation

Y. Kuno

Research Center of Nuclear Physics, Osaka University

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Abstract

Charged lepton flavour violation (CLFV) represents a tantalizing window into physics beyond the Standard Model (SM). This manuscript highlights the significance of CLFV, in particular with muons, and their experimental searches.

1 CLFV Motivation for New Physics Searches

In the minimal Standard Model (SM), neutrinos were thought to be massless, and lepton flavor conservation was believed to hold within each generation. However, neutrino oscillation experiments revealed that neutrinos have mass and can mix flavors, disproving lepton flavor conservation. However, the SM predicts an extremely small contribution to charged lepton flavor violation (CLFV) rates, like $\mu^+ \rightarrow e^+\gamma$, which can be calculated using the PMNS lepton mixing matrix [1, 2, 3, 4]. This contribution is astonishingly small, approximately at the rate of 10^{-54} , mostly due to the GIM suppression from the neutrino mass squared difference and the W mass, offering a unique experimental avenue to explore new physics beyond the SM (BSM) without significant interference from SM backgrounds.

To assess CLFV sensitivity, an effective field theory (EFT) approach is employed. The effective Lagrangian (\mathcal{L}) includes both the SM Lagrangian and higher-dimensional operators, characterized by the coupling constant (C) and energy scale (Λ) of new physics. Current constraints from the CLFV searches indicate a potential energy scale $\Lambda \sim \mathcal{O}(10^4)$ TeV, with a coupling constant C of $\mathcal{O}(1)$ [5].

Ongoing and upcoming experiments exhibit remarkable sensitivity improvements, aiming to surpass current limits by more than 10,000 times. The introduction of dimension-six operators implies that the rate scales inversely with Λ^4 , extending the potential energy reach to $\mathcal{O}(10^5)$ TeV in the future.

Several theoretical models predict significant CLFV rates, some appearing just below the current experimental limits. These models involve neutral heavy leptons, extra dimensions, Z' bosons, leptoquarks, supersymmetry, and more. These models suggest hope for groundbreaking discoveries in the realm of CLFV phenomena.

2 Muon CLFV

The most sensitive studies of CLFV are made by experiments to searches for $\mu \rightarrow e$ transitions by utilizing highly intense muon sources [6]. They are $\mu^+ \rightarrow e^+\gamma$, $\mu^+ \rightarrow e^+e^-e^+$, and $\mu^- \rightarrow e^-$ conversion in a muonic atom. The significance of CLFV physics is highlighted through all three muon processes: $\mu^+ \rightarrow e^+\gamma$ results from the dipole photonic interaction. $\mu^+ \rightarrow e^+e^-e^+$ involves the dipole photonic interaction and four-fermion contact interactions with one muon and three electrons. $\mu^- \rightarrow e^-$ conversion encompasses the dipole photonic interaction and four-fermion contact interactions with a muon, an electron, and quarks. Constructing new physics models at high energy scales, which are then brought to experimental scales, leads to mixing various operators through quantum corrections [7, 8]. Hence, a comprehensive investigation of all three muon CLFV processes is required to disentangle their respective contributions and gain a complete grasp of the new physics underlying CLFV phenomena [9].

2.1 $\mu^+ \rightarrow e^+\gamma$

The event signature of $\mu^+ \rightarrow e^+\gamma$ decay at rest involves a positron and a photon are moving back-to-back in time coincidence, each with an energy equal to half the muon mass ($m_\mu/2 = 52.8$ MeV). This process has been studied in the past using decays of positive muons at rest to utilize its kinematics.

Two primary backgrounds challenge the $\mu^+ \rightarrow e^+\gamma$ search: one of them is radiative muon decay ($\mu^+ \rightarrow e^+\nu\bar{\nu}\gamma$) where back-to-back emission of e^+ and a photon with neutrinos carrying small energy. The other is accidental coincidence of a high-energy photon with a positron from normal muon decay. Potential sources

of high-energy photon include $\mu^+ \rightarrow e^+ \nu \bar{\nu} \gamma$ decay, annihilation-in-flight of a e^+ , or external bremsstrahlung. Mitigating accidental background events necessitates a low incident muon rate, achievable through continuous muon beams.

The current upper limit for $\mu^+ \rightarrow e^+ \gamma$ is $\text{BR}(\mu^+ \rightarrow e^+ \gamma) < 4.2 \times 10^{-13}$ at 90% confidence level (CL) [10], established by the MEG experiment (2009–2013) utilizing a 28 MeV/c monochromatic surface muon beam, drift chambers, and a liquid xenon photon detector within a graded magnetic field solenoid.

MEG II [11, 12] features an improved e^+ spectrometer made of a new cylindrical drift chamber, pixelated precision timing counters, a liquid xenon photon detector with silicon photomultipliers on the front face, and an added detector for $\mu^+ \rightarrow e^+ \nu \bar{\nu} \gamma$ background suppression. Expected resolutions are approximately twice as precise as MEG, enabling higher muon beam intensity utilization. MEG II targets a tenfold sensitivity increase, aspiring for 6×10^{-14} . By running since 2021, MEG II operations continue through 2025 or 2026.

2.2 $\mu^+ \rightarrow e^+ e^- e^+$

The event signature of $\mu^+ \rightarrow e^+ e^- e^+$ decay is kinematically constrained, ensuring a well-defined event signature, with all final-state particles precisely detectable. Historical experiments relied on positive muon decays at rest, exploiting momentum and energy conservation ($|\sum_i \vec{p}_i| = 0$ and $\sum_i E_i = m_\mu$) alongside timing coincidences between two e^+ s and one e^- .

Two main backgrounds challenge $\mu^+ \rightarrow e^+ e^- e^+$ investigations. One of them is the allowed muon decay $\mu^+ \rightarrow e^+ \nu \bar{\nu} e^+ e^-$ ($\text{BR} = (3.4 \pm 0.4) \times 10^{-5}$) which becomes prominent when ν_e and $\bar{\nu}_\mu$ have low energies. The other background involves accidental coincidence between a e^+ from normal muon decay and an uncorrelated $e^+ e^-$ pair, originating from Bhabha scattering or external conversion of $\mu^+ \rightarrow e^+ \nu e \bar{\nu} \mu \gamma$ decay. Similar to the $\mu^+ \rightarrow e^+ \gamma$ search, a continuous muon beam is a key to reducing accidental background events.

The present experimental limit, $\text{BR}(\mu^+ \rightarrow e^+ e^- e^+) < 1 \times 10^{-12}$ at 90% CL, was established by the SINDRUM experiment (1983–1986) [13], assuming a constant matrix element for $\mu^+ \rightarrow e^+ e^- e^+$ decay spectrum.

Mu3e, with its first stage, aims for $\text{BR}(\mu^+ \rightarrow e^+ e^- e^+) < 5 \times 10^{-15}$ at 90% CL at the $\pi E5$ beamline at PSI [14]. Employing ultra-thin silicon pixel tracking detectors based on HV-MAPS technology and a high time resolution scintillating fiber system, all within a 1 T magnetic field solenoid, Mu3e Phase-I anticipates its physics running from 2026. The Phase-I sensitivity is constrained by the muon rate at $\pi E5$, while a new High Intensity Muon Beamline (HiMB) [15] will be constructed from 2027–2028 at PSI, projecting about 10^{10} surface μ^+ s/second. Mu3e Phase-II, building upon HiMB, targets another tenfold enhancement, aiming for $\text{BR}(\mu^+ \rightarrow e^+ e^- e^+) < 1 \times 10^{-16}$ at 90% CL.

2.3 $\mu^- \rightarrow e^-$ conversion in a muonic atom

The third important $\mu \rightarrow e$ transition process is neutrino-less conversion of a negative muon to an electron in the field of a nucleus of a muonic atom, $\mu^- N(A, Z) \rightarrow e^- N(A, Z)$. The final state of the nucleus $N(A, Z)$ could be either the ground state or one of the excited states. In general, the transition to the ground state, which is called coherent conversion, is dominant. The rate of the coherent capture over non-coherent capture is enhanced by a factor approximately equal to the number of nucleons in the nucleus. The conversion rate of $\mu^- \rightarrow e^-$ conversion is defined as $\text{CR}(\mu^- N \rightarrow e^- N) \equiv \Gamma(\mu^- N \rightarrow e^- N) / \Gamma(\mu^- N \rightarrow \text{all})$, where Γ is the rate. The

time distribution of $\mu^- \rightarrow e^-$ conversion follows a lifetime of a muonic atom, which depends on a nucleus.

The event signature of $\mu^- \rightarrow e^-$ conversion in a muonic atom is a mono-energetic single electron emitted from the conversion with an energy ($E_{\mu e}$) of $E_{\mu e} = m_\mu - B_\mu - E_{recoil}$, where m_μ is the muon mass, and B_μ is the binding energy of the 1s muonic atom. E_{recoil} is the nuclear recoil energy. Since B_μ varies for various nuclei, $E_{\mu e}$ could be different. For instance, $E_{\mu e} = 104.9$ MeV for aluminium (Al), $E_{\mu e} = 104.3$ MeV for titanium (Ti), and $E_{\mu e} = 94.9$ MeV for lead (Pb). The potential background sources for $\mu^- \rightarrow e^-$ conversion searches can be grouped into three. The first group is intrinsic physics backgrounds which come from muons stopped in the muon-stopping target, such as electrons from muon decays in orbit and radiative muon capture. The second is beam-related backgrounds which are caused by beam particles in a muon beam. To eliminate beam-related backgrounds, a pulsed proton beam is used and the measurement will be made between the beam pulses. The third is backgrounds coming from cosmic-ray muons, fake tracking events, and so on.

The effective Lagrangian of $\mu^- \rightarrow e^-$ conversion can be expressed by dipole, scalar, vector, pseudo-scalar, axial-vector and tensor interactions. Among these effective interactions, the dipole, scalar and vector operators contribute to the spin independent (SI) $\mu^- \rightarrow e^-$ conversion processes, whereas the axial, tensor and pseudo-scalar operators contribute to the spin dependent (SD) $\mu^- \rightarrow e^-$ conversion [16, 17]. The SI process is a coherent process which does benefit from nucleon-number-squared enhancement, but the SD process does not. The rates of the SI processes for various nuclei were calculated, showing the dependence of atomic charge (Z) could be used to discriminate different type of effective interactions [18, 19, 20, 21].

The past experimental searches for $\mu^- \rightarrow e^-$ conversion were made with five different materials of muon stopping targets, such as sulphur ($Z=16$), titanium ($Z=22$), copper ($Z=39$), gold ($Z=79$), and lead ($Z=82$). Among them, the best limit is $\text{CR}(\mu^- \text{Au} \rightarrow e^- \text{Au}) < 7 \times 10^{-13}$ at 90% CL, which was obtained by the SINDRUM-II experiment, from data collected from 2000 [22].

There are two new experiments to search for $\mu^- \rightarrow e^-$ conversion under preparation; one is the COMET experiment in Japan, and the other is the Mu2e experiment in the US.

The COMET experiment at J-PARC aims to achieve $\text{CR}(\mu^- \text{Al} \rightarrow e^- \text{Al}) < 6 \times 10^{-17}$ at a 90% CL with 56 kW proton beam power for 230 days of operation. The COMET experiment has taken a two-staged approach. The COMET Phase-I [23], the first stage of the experiment, is aiming at $\text{CR}(\mu^- \text{Al} \rightarrow e^- \text{Al}) < 7 \times 10^{-15}$ at 90% CL for 150 days of operation. An 8 GeV pulsed proton beam with 3.2 kW from the J-PARC main ring will be delivered to a proton target made of graphite inside the 5 T pion capture solenoid. The muon transport consists of a 90-degree curved solenoids, together with dipole coils installed inside the solenoids, providing momentum and charged selection by changing a dipole magnetic field. The detector to search for $\mu^- \rightarrow e^-$ conversion in COMET Phase-I is a cylindrical drift chamber. And low-mass straw tube drift chambers and a LYSO crystal calorimeter, which are the COMET Phase-II detector, will be used for beam measurement in COMET Phase-I. The entire detector is surrounded by a cosmic veto system made of plastic scintillators. The COMET Phase-I will be extended to COMET Phase-II. The proton target for Phase-II is made of tungsten. The muon transport at Phase-II consists of two 90-degree curved solenoids with the same bending direction, forming a “C” shape, where continuous 180-degree bend will be fully utilized to make twice better momentum and charge separation than single 90-degree bend. The electron

transport, which is installed between the muon target and the detector, has a 180-degree curved solenoid to select 105 MeV/ c electrons and eliminate positive-charged particles (such as protons from muon capture) and low energy electrons from normal muon decays. This curved electron transport also eliminates a direct sight from the detector to the muon target to remove neutron and γ -ray backgrounds, which would otherwise cause serious high detector rates. Recently, further improvements of sensitivity by one order of magnitude, yielding a sensitivity of $\mathcal{O}(10^{-18})$, from refinements to the experimental design, such as further optimized electron transport, and operation are being considered [24].

The Mu2e experiment at Fermilab [25, 26, 27] aims to achieve $\text{CR}(\mu^- Al \rightarrow e^- Al) < 8 \times 10^{-17}$ at 90% CL. The experiment employs a 8 GeV pulsed proton beam at 8 kW from the Fermilab Booster, delivered with 1.7 μs intervals. These protons interact with a tungsten proton target located within high magnetic-field solenoids. Production of muons from pion decays are directed through two 90-degree curved solenoids, creating an “S” shape trajectory. The first bend’s collimators select momentum and charge, while the second bend centralizes muons within the beamline. Subsequently, the muons encounter a muon stopping target situated in a graded magnetic field. The experiment employs a detector system, featuring straw tube drift chambers and an electron calorimeter composed of pure CsI crystals, all within a uniform magnetic field region. Surrounding the entire detector is a cosmic veto system made of scintillator materials. Their first data taking run, Run-I, is planning to start in 2026 until the accelerator shutdown for the PIP-II construction in 2027-2028, aiming a factor of 1000 improvement over the current limit, and the Run-II data taking will resume after it, in 2029.

Future prospects include the potential upgrade to Mu2e-II [28], capitalizing on the high-intensity proton beam offered by the PIP-II project. This initiative could yield up to 100 kW of 0.8 GeV protons out of 1.6 MW from the PIP-II linac, significantly enhancing Mu2e-II’s sensitivity by a factor of ten or more. Such endeavors underscore the experiment’s commitment to pushing boundaries and advancing our understanding of particle physics.

3 Future Prospects

In the long term future, the development of a high-intensity muon beam with improved emittance stands as a crucial step for substantial advancements in muon CLFV experiments. Novel techniques like phase rotation and beam cooling, pioneered in muon collider and neutrino factory R&D, offer potential avenues for creating muon beams with better beam emittance. The PRISM (Phase Rotated Intense Muon Source) concept [29, 30], tested in Japan, exploits phase rotation within a muon storage ring based on a fixed-field alternating gradient synchrotron (FFA). The PRISM allows $\mu^- \rightarrow e^-$ conversion experiments with high Z muon stopping targets with negligible pion contamination after their long flight path in the storage ring. The successful demonstration of phase rotation within the PRISM project at Osaka University in 2008 supports these innovative pursuits.

Proposed as an important undertaking for the forthcoming phase of precision muon experiments encompassing both μ^\pm s, the Advanced Muon Facility (AMF) at Fermilab [31] is proposed by utilizing PIP-II and the Accelerator Evolution (ACE) framework. Scheduled for realization in the 2040s, AMF’s blueprint encompasses a FFA ring, enabling the next generation of precision muon CLFV experiments, thereby making a way towards unprecedented development for muon CLFV researches.

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